

THE SOCIAL - PHILOSOPHICAL NECESSITY OF FORMING HARMONY AND CONSISTENCY IN THE DIALECTICS OF SOCIETY

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Abstract: In the present article, the phenomenon of cultural interaction in literature in the context of societal development is being actively discussed. According to this interaction, each nation, preserving its independent, unique, and culturally rich style, has strengthened the process of social development as its own model, using the experiences of other nations judiciously. This has been highlighted as the consolidation of social progress in the form of a distinctive model through the creative utilization of the experiences of other nations, while maintaining its own stable, noble, and culturally oriented way.

Keywords: social development, social structure, consistency, moral-ethical, cultural development, spiritual values, national identity, cultural heritage, state history, intellectual work, science.

At each stage of social development, there is a need for theoretical knowledge that explains life on the basis of new thinking. This issue is undoubtedly interconnected with philosophical contemplation. How should people choose their path, what should be the foundation of their activities? In what way is it necessary to fulfill people's dreams and wishes? What is the meaning of living? Responding to these questions is associated with the creation of a new thinking system. The effective functioning of various political institutions (government, political parties, organizations, various associations) plays a crucial role in managing both the material and spiritual life of society, organizing relationships between individuals, and maintaining order. The political and legal aspects of governance are also essential. The deepening of political and legal knowledge by individuals contributes significantly to the sustainable development and progress of society. As a result of the social distribution based on the abilities of individuals in the field of labor, certain professions - jobs that can be engaged with specific skills - groups, layers, and classes emerge, and they occupy a unique place in the social structure, contributing to the development of society.

In the history of philosophical thought, various theories exist regarding the essence and development of society. Specifically, in the philosophical history, German philosopher Hegel explained the formation and development of society

as the absolute spirit's development. L. Feuerbach, particularly connected with religion, presented the societal development reasons from the standpoint of religious consciousness. French theorist A. Comte explained the causes of societal development in three stages of the spiritual progress of humanity (theological, metaphysical, and positive stages).

Social development involves several stages, according to the perspectives presented by American futurist A. Toffler. According to this viewpoint, society is categorized into agrarian, industrial, and post-industrial stages. In literature, the idea of societal development is actively discussed. According to this concept, each nation, while preserving its independent, unique, and culturally rich style, creates its own distinctive model of social development by creatively utilizing the experiences of other nations. Stability and diversity are crucial aspects of societal life. Just as each individual needs simplicity and peace to achieve their goals, society also requires social and political stability to fulfill its tasks effectively.

Sustainability is the historical development of societal progress, representing the potential for a continuous and coordinated activity within a certain degree of the social system. It sharply differs in perception from instability. The socio-political perception of instability indicates the manifestation of the existing political, economic, and moral systems in society. It is possible for sustainability and instability to coexist, harmonizing and intertwining with growth and decline in society. Achieving specific milestones in the spiritual, economic, political, and legal domains of society, followed by the emergence of new challenges, marks the path of societal development after reaching initial achievements and poses the task of resolving them. In this regard, it is worth emphasizing that the ideas of the ancient Chinese philosopher Confucius (551-479 BCE) are noteworthy, and he imparts such wisdom: "If you learn the fundamentals and principles of rituals and ceremonies and understand the ideas about goodness and wickedness (moral knowledge), you will reach the highest level of integrity. If your intentions are pure and sincere, your heart will be straightforward and honest. If your heart is straightforward and honest, you will enter the path of righteousness and attain benevolence. When a person follows the right path and attains benevolence, order is established in the family. When order is established in the family, governing the people becomes easy. When governing the people becomes easy, the whole world lives in peace and harmony."

Instability arises as a result of internal and external processes and conflicts. During periods of transitioning from one social-political system to another, instability may undergo significant intensification. The emergence of societal instability is evident in negative changes in individual psychology, the enforcement of laws, the resilience of social structures, the absence of conformity to societal ideals, the increase of indifference to ideas and ideologies, the emergence of various criminal groups, the breakdown of social justice norms, the weakening of the governance capacity of state institutions, and the exacerbation of various conflicts.

The experience of the world shows that having the right to choose the path of development for each country and its people is the key to ensuring overall security and social stability. The new Uzbekistan national statehood aims to strengthen its national identity, choose its own distinctive and compatible path of development, and provide opportunities through a strategy of development for progress. The Uzbek model of social progress aligns with the rich experience of human development, our national statehood, and the mentality of our people. In the process of social progress, nations usually follow one of two paths: either the revolutionary or the evolutionary path. Human experience indicates that the sharp, revolutionary changes of social progress are often unpredictable and useless, while the societal evolutionary development is stable and follows a natural course.

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